

Strong Perfect Metro Domination in Graphs

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Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected graph. A metro dominating set $D \subseteq V(G)$ is called strong perfect metro dominating set of G if $|N_s(u) \cap D| = 1, \forall u \in V(G) \setminus D$ and $N_s(u) = \{v \in V(G) / \deg(v) \geq \deg(u)\}$, $N_w(u) = \{v \in V(G) / \deg(v) < \deg(u)\}$. For the minimum cardinality of a strong(weak) perfect metro domination set G is called the strong(weak) perfect metro domination number and it is denoted by $\gamma_{sp\beta}(G)$ or $\gamma_{wp\beta}(G)$.

This study calculates the strong perfect metro domination number and power of several common graphs.

Keywords: Dominating set, Perfect dominating set, Strong dominating set, Strong perfect dominating set, Metro dominating set, Power graph, Ladder graph.

1 Introduction

By a graph G , We means a finite, connected and undirected graph without loops and parallel edges with vertex set $V(G)$ and edge set $E(G)$ [8]. For any vertex $v \in V(G)$, the open neighbourhood of v is $N(v) = \{u \in V(G) : uv \in E(G)\}$ and the close neighbourhood of v is $N[v] = N(v) \cup v$. A set $M \subseteq V(G)$ is dominating set of G if every $v \in V(G) \setminus M$ such that $m \in M, vm \in E(G)$. The minimum cardinality of dominating set M is called domination number denoted by $\gamma(G)$ [3]. A dominating set M is of the smallest possible size in graph G is called minimum dominating set. A subset $M \subseteq V(G)$ is perfect dominating set if each vertex $v \in V(G) \setminus M$ is adjacent to exactly one vertex in M . The minimum cardinality of perfect dominating set M is called perfect domination number denoted by $\gamma_p(G)$ [7]. A subset $M \subseteq V(G)$ is called strong dominating set of G if for every vertex $x \in V(G) \setminus M$ there is a vertex $y \in M$

with $xy \in E(G)$ and $\deg(x) \leq \deg(y)$. The strong domination number $\gamma_s(G)$ is defined as the minimum cardinality $\gamma_s(G)$ is called γ_s -set [6]. A dominating set D of $V(G)$ having for each pair of vertices u, v there exists a vertex w in D such that $d(u, w) \neq d(v, w)$ is called metro dominating set of G it is denoted by MD-set. The minimum cardinality of a metro dominating set of G is called metro domination number of G it is denoted by $\gamma_\beta(G)$ [1]. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a connected graph. A metro dominating set $D \subseteq V(G)$ is called strong perfect metro dominating set of G if $|N_S(u) \cap D| = 1, \forall u \in V(G) \setminus D$ and $N_s(u) = \{v \in V(G) / \deg(v) \geq \deg(u)\}, N_w(u) = \{v \in V(G) / \deg(v) < \deg(u)\}$. where N_s are strong neighborhood and N_w are weak neighborhood. For the minimum cardinality of a strong perfect metro domination set G is called the strong perfect metro domination number and it is denoted by $\gamma_{sp\beta}(G)$ or $\gamma_{wp\beta}(G)$.

Let $G = (V, E)$ be any connected graph and their k^{th} power is denoted by G^k whose vertex is same as that of G and two vertices (u, v) in G^k are adjacent to k if and only if $d(u, v) \leq k$ in G [4]. Note that $k \in N$.

2 Main Results:

Theorem 2.1 Let $G = P_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil \text{ for } n \geq 3$$

Proof : Let D be a metro dominating set p_n . Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n are the vertices of p_n such that u_i is adjacent to u_{i+1} for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$.

Since a strong perfect metro dominating set is also a metro dominating set than

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil \quad (1)$$

D is strong perfect metro dominating set follows $u_j \in V-D$.

Now we want to prove following three cases

- (1) $D = \{3k; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$
- (2) $D = \{u_{3k+2}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$
- (3) $D = \{u_{3k+1}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

Case (1) : for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

Let $D = \{3k; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n-2$

Then $|D| = \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$

D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V-D$

Then D is at least one of u_{j+1} and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set so it is also strong perfect dominating set

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$$

Case (2) : for $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Let $D = \{u_{3k+2}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n-1$

Then $|D| = \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$

D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V-D$

Then D is at least one of u_{j+1} and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set so it is also strong perfect dominating set.

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \left\lceil \frac{n}{3} \right\rceil$$

Case (3) : for $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

Let $D = \{u_{3k+1}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n$

Then $|D| = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil$
 D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V - D$

Then D is atleast one of u_{j+1} and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set so it is also strong perfect dominating set.

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil \tag{1}$$

If u_{j+1} and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set then it is also strong perfect dominating set

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil \tag{2}$$

So, from the equation (1) & (2)

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil$$

Thus, show the result.

Lemma 2.2 Let $G = P_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil & ; \text{if } n \geq 11 \\ n & ; \text{if } n < 11 \end{cases}$$

Proof : = Let D be a metro dominating set P_n^2 . Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices of P_n^2 such that u_i is adjacent to u_{i+1} for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n - 1$.

Since a strong perfect metro dominating set is also a metro dominating set than

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \geq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil \tag{1}$$

By using the method of inverted inequality, we find a strong perfect metro dominating set as follows:

$$(1) D = \{5k; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 0(\text{mod}5)$$

$$(2) D = \{u_{5k-4}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 1(\text{mod}5)$$

$$(3) D = \{u_{5k-3}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 2(\text{mod}5)$$

$$(4) D = \{u_{5k-2}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 3(\text{mod}5)$$

$$(5) D = \{u_{5k-1}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 4(\text{mod}5)$$

Case (1): for $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}5)$

Let $D = \{5k; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 0(\text{mod}5)$

$$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n - 4$$

Then $|D| = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$

D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V - D$

Then D is atleast one of $u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}$ and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set so it is also strong perfect dominating set .

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

Case (2): for $n \equiv 1(\text{mod}5)$

Let $D = \{u_{5k-4}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 1(\text{mod}5)$

$$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n - 3$$

Then $|D| = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$

D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V - D$

Then D is atleast one of $u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}$ and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set so it is also strong perfect dominating set

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

Case (3): for $n \equiv 2(\text{mod}5)$

Let $D = \{u_{5k-3}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 2(\text{mod}5)$

$$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n - 2$$

Then $|D| = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$

D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V - D$

Then D is atleast one of $u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}$ and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set so it is also strong perfect dominating set

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

Case (4): for $n \equiv 3(\text{mod}5)$

Let $D = \{u_{5k-2}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 3(\text{mod}5)$

$$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n - 1$$

$$\text{Then } |D| = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V - D$

Thus D is atleast one of $u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}$ and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set so it is clear that strong perfect dominating set.

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

Case (5): for $n \equiv 4(\text{mod}5)$

Let $D = \{u_{5k-1}; k \geq 1\} n \equiv 4(\text{mod}5)$

$$\therefore 1 \leq k \leq n$$

$$\text{Then } |D| = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

D is a metro dominating set follows every $u_j \in V - D$

Then D is atleast one of $u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}$ or u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set then it is also strong perfect dominating set.

Thus u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil \tag{1}$$

D is strong perfect metro dominating set.

Then every $u_j \in V - D$

if $u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}$ and u_{j+2} must be metro dominating set then it is also strong perfect dominating set

Then u_j are dominates.

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil \tag{2}$$

So , from the equation (1) & (2)

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

Therefore in above all the cases $\gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$. Thus we obtain $\gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil, \forall n \geq 11$ if $n < 11$ then we observe that. $\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^2) = n$. Hence prove the result.

Lemma 2.3 Let $G = P_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(P_n^3) = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil & ; \text{ if } n \geq 22 \\ n & ; \text{ if } n < 22 \end{cases}$$

Proof: In P_n^3 , consider any v_j and $v_{j+7}, j \geq 4$ in D. Vertex v_j dominates $v_{j-3}, v_{j-2}, v_{j-1}, v_{j+1}, v_{j+2}, v_{j+3}$. Vertex v_{j+7} dominates $v_{j+4}, v_{j+5}, v_{j+6}, v_{j+8}, v_{j+9}$ and v_{j+10} .

These vertices are uniquely dominated by v_j and v_{j+7} . The vertices v_1, v_2 and v_3 are uniquely dominated by v_4 . The vertex v_{7K}, v_{7K-1} and v_{7K-2} are uniquely dominated by v_{7K-3} .

If $j > i + 14$, then $(v_i, v_j) = \lceil \frac{j-i-i}{3} \rceil, d(v_{j+7}, v_j) = \lceil \frac{i-i-7}{3} \rceil$ and $d(v_i + 14, v_j) = \lceil \frac{j-i-14}{3} \rceil$. Hence if $j = 3k$ and $j > i + 14$ then $d(v_i, v_{j-1}) = d(v_i, v_j) = d(v_i, v_{j+1})$, whereas $d(v_{j+7}, v_j) = d(v_{j+7}, v_{j+1}) = d(v_{i+2}, v_{j+2})$ and $d(v_{i+14}, v_{i+1}) =$

$d(v_{i+14}, v_{j+2}) = d(v_{j+2}, v_{j+3})$. Hence codes generated by v_i, v_{i+7}, v_{i+14} to $v_j, j > i + 14$ are all distinct and therefore $\{v_i, v_{i+7}, v_{i+14}\}$ resolves them. Now take $j = 3k, i < j < i + 7$.

Note that $d(v_j, v_{j-1}) = d(v_i, v_j) = d(v_i, v_{j+1}), d(v_{j+2}, v_{j-1}) = d(v_{j+2}, v_j) = d(v_{j+7}, v_{j+1})$ and $d(v_{i+14}, v_j) = d(v_{i+14}, v_{j+1}) = d(v_{i+14}, v_{j+2})$. Hence codes generated by $\{v_i, v_{i+7}, v_{i+14}\}$ to v_j and v_{j+1} is the same. Observe that if $r < i + 21$ then $(v_{i+21}, v_r) = \lceil \frac{i+21-r}{3} \rceil$. Hence $(v_{i+21}, v_j) \neq d(v_{i+21}, v_{j+1})$. Therefore $\{v_i, v_{i+7}, v_{i+14}, v_{i+21}\} v_j$ resolves $v_j, i < j < i + 7$.

In a similar vein we observe that codes generated by $\{v_i, v_{i+7}, v_{i+14}\}$ to and $v_j + 1$ where $i + 7 < j = 3k < i + 14$ are same. But $(v_{i+21}, v_j) \neq d(v_{i+21}, v_{j+1})$. Hence $\{v_i, v_{i+7}, v_{i+14}, v_{i+21}\}$ settles all vertices $v_j, j > i$. When $i = 4$, the codes generated by $\{v_4, v_{11}, v_{18}, v_{25}\}$ to v_1, v_2 and v_3 are $(1, 4, 6, 8), (1, 3, 6, 8), (1, 3, 5, 8)$ and hence $\{v_4, v_{11}, v_{18}, v_{25}\}$ resolves all vertices of p_n^3 . Therefore to resolve all vertices of p_n^3 we take $n \geq 22$.

We observe that $D = \{v_4, v_{11}, v_{18}, \dots, v_{7k+3}, v_{7k+4}\}$ is a strong perfect metro dominating set. Therefore $\gamma_\beta(p_n^3) = k = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil$. When $n = 7k + 1, 7k + 2, 7k + 3$ and $7k + 4, D = \{v_4, v_8, v_{15}, \dots, v_{7k+6}, v_{7k+1}\}$ is a strong perfect metro dominating set. When $n = 7k + 5, 7k + 6$ we have $D = \{v_4, v_{11}, v_{18}, \dots, v_{7k+3}, v_{7k+4}\}$ is a strong perfect metro dominating set.

Therefore $\gamma_\beta(p_n^3) = k + 1$. In in above

all the cases $|D| = k + 1 = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil$. Thus we obtain that $\gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^3) = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil, \forall n \geq 22$. If $n < 22$, then we observe that $\gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^3) = n$. Hence prove the result.

Theorem 2.4 Let $G = p_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^k) = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{n}{2k+1} \rceil & ; \text{ if } n \geq 2k^2 + k + 1 \\ n & ; \text{ if } n < 2k^2 + k + 1 \end{cases}$$

Proof :Let D be a metro dominating set p_n . Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices of c_n such that u_i for $2 \leq i \leq n - 1$

Now vertices $u_i,$
Then $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2k + 1}$

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^k) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \right\rceil \quad (1)$$

Let D be a metro dominating set of G each vertex of D dominates at most $2k + 1$ vertices of c_n .

Then $c_n = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n)$ of order $n \equiv (2k + 1)l$ for some $l \geq 1$.

We define D

$$D = \left\{ u(2k + 1)l + 1 \quad l = 0, 1, \dots, \left\lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \right\rceil - 1 \right\}$$

D is a strong metro dominating set of c_n .

Then for $u_j \in V - D$

If atleast one D of $n \equiv 2k \pmod{2k + 1}$) must be dominates u_j

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^k) \geq \left\lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \right\rceil \quad (2)$$

So, from the equation (1) & (2)

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^k) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \right\rceil$$

Thus, show the result.

Therefore in above all the cases $\gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^k) = \lceil \frac{n}{2k+1} \rceil$. Thus we obtain $\gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^k) = \lceil \frac{n}{2k+1} \rceil, \forall n \geq 2k^2 + k + 1$ if $n < 2k^2 + k + 1$ then we observe that. $\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(p_n^k) = n$. Hence prove the result.

Theorem 2.5 Let $G = c_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil \text{ for } n \geq 7$$

Proof :Let D be a metro dominating set c_n . Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices of c_n such that u_i is adjacent to u_{i+1} for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$.

We know that $\beta_\beta(c_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil$

Since a strong perfect metro dominating set is also metro dominating set .

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n) \geq \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil \tag{1}$$

By using the method of inverted inequality,

$$D = \{u_i + (3k + 2); k \geq 1\}$$

Then D is strong perfect metro dominating set .

for $u_j \in V - D$

If atleast one D is u_{j-1}, u_{j+1} or u_{j+2} must be strong perfect dominates of u_j .

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil \tag{2}$$

So, from the equation (1) & (2)

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil$$

Thus, show the result.

Lemma 2.6 Let $G = c_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^2) = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil & ; \text{ if } n \geq 11 \\ n & ; \text{ if } n < 11 \end{cases}$$

Proof : Let D be a metro dominating set c_n . Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices of c_n such that u_i is adjacent to u_{i+1} for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$.

We know that $\beta_\beta(c_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$

Since a strong perfect metro dominating set is also metro dominating set .

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^2) \geq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil \tag{1}$$

By using the method of inverted inequality,

$$D = \{u_i + (5k - 2); k \geq 1\}$$

Then D is strong perfect metro dominating set.

If atleast one D is $u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}$ or u_{j+2} must be strong perfect dominates of u_j .

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^2) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil \tag{2}$$

So, from the equation (1) & (2)

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^2) = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$$

Thus, show the result.

Therefore in above all the cases $\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^2) = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil$. Thus we obtain $\gamma_{sp\beta\beta}(c_n^2) = \lceil \frac{n}{5} \rceil, \forall n \geq 11$ if $n < 11$ then we observe that $\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^2) = n$. Hence prove the result.

Lemma 2.7 Let $G = c_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil & ; \text{ if } n \geq 22 \\ n & ; \text{ if } n < 22 \end{cases}$$

Proof :Let D be a metro dominating set c_n . Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices of c_n such that u_i is adjacent to u_{i+1} for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n - 1$.

We know that $p_\beta(c_n) = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil$

Since a strong perfect metro dominating set is also metro dominating set .

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) \geq \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil \tag{1}$$

By using the method of inverted inequality,

$$D = \{u_i + (7k - 2); k = 0, 1, \dots, \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil - 1\}$$

Then D is strong perfect metro dominating set .

for $u_j \in V - D$

If at least one D is $u_{j-3}, u_{j-2}, u_{j-1}, u_{j+1}, u_{j+2}$ or u_{j+3} must be strong perfect dominates of u_j .

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) \leq \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil \tag{2}$$

So, from the equation (1) & (2)

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil$$

Thus, show the result.

Therefore in above all the cases $\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil$. Thus we obtain $\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) = \lceil \frac{n}{7} \rceil, \forall n \geq 11$ if $n < 11$ then we observe that. $\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) = n$. Hence prove the result.

Theorem 2.8 Let $G = c_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^3) = \begin{cases} \lceil \frac{n}{2k+1} \rceil & ; \text{if } n \geq 2k^2 + k + 1 \\ n & ; \text{if } n < 2k^2 + k + 1 \end{cases}$$

Proof :Let D be a metro dominating set c_n . Let u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n be vertices of c_n such that u_i for $2 \leq i \leq n - 1$

Now vertices u_i ,

Then $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2k + 1}$

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^k) \geq \lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \rceil \tag{1}$$

Let D be a metro dominating set of G each vertex of D dominates at most $2k + 1$ vertices of c_n .

Then $c_n = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n)$ of order $n \equiv (2k + 1)l$ for some $l \geq 1$.

We define D

$$D = \left\{ u(2k + 1)l + 1 \quad l = 0, 1, \dots, \left\lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \right\rceil - 1 \right\}$$

D is a strong metro dominating set of c_n .

Then for $u_j \in V - D$

If at least one D of $n \equiv 2k \pmod{2k + 1}$) must be dominates u_j

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^k) \geq \lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \rceil \tag{2}$$

So, from the equation (1) & (2)

$$\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^k) = \lceil \frac{n}{2k + 1} \rceil$$

Thus, show the result.

Therefore in above all the cases $\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^k) = \lceil \frac{n}{2k+1} \rceil$. Thus we obtain $\gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^k) = \lceil \frac{n}{2k+1} \rceil, \forall n \geq 2k^2 + k + 1$ if $n < 2k^2 + k + 1$ then we observe that. $\therefore \gamma_{sp\beta}(c_n^k) = n$. Hence prove the result.

Theorem 2.9 Let $G = L_n$ then

$$\gamma_{sp\beta}(L_n) = \left\lceil \frac{n + 1}{2} \right\rceil \text{ for } n \geq 3$$

Figure 1: $n = 4k+1$

Proof : Let D be a metro dominating set L_n . Let $v_{1,1}, v_{1,2}, \dots, v_{i,j}$ be vertices of L_n .

Case (1): $n = 4k + 1$, then $|D| = \lceil \frac{n+1}{2} \rceil$

The set D is $\{v_{1+4i,1}, v_{3+4j,2} : 0 \leq 1 + 4i \leq n, 0 \leq 3 + 4j \leq n\}$

On the first horizontal projection H_1 , when $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n-1}{4} \rfloor$; $k + 1$ vertices $v_{1,1}, v_{5,1}, \dots, v_{n,1}$ are in D . On the second horizontal projection H_2 when $j = 0, 1, \dots, \lfloor \frac{n-1}{4} \rfloor - 1$; k vertices $v_{3,2}, v_{7,2}, \dots, v_{n-2,2}$, are in D . Thus, D has $k + 1 + k$ vertices. Therefore, $|D| = 2k + 1 = 2 \lfloor \frac{n-1}{4} \rfloor + 1 = \lceil \frac{n+1}{2} \rceil$.

Case (2): if $n = 4k + 3$, then $|D| = \lceil \frac{n+1}{2} \rceil$

Figure 2: $n = 4k+3$

On the first horizontal projection $H_1, v_{1,1}, v_{5,1}, \dots, v_{4K+1,1}$ are in D and on the second horizontal projection H_2 , vertices $v_{3,2}, v_{7,2}, \dots, v_{4K+3,2}$, are in D . Thus, $k + 1$ vertices on the first horizontal projection H_1 and $k + 1$ vertices on the second horizontal projection H_2 are in D .

Hence $|D| = 2k + 2 = \lceil \frac{n-3}{2} \rceil + 2 = \lceil \frac{n+1}{2} \rceil$. Thus, show the result.

3 Conclusion

In this paper, we present the idea of strong perfect metro domination and establish the framework for investigating its related parameter. The paper presents theorems that are easily understood when viewed in the context of the presented notions and are stated in a clear and concise manner. We suggest investigating a number of novel graph families as a potential avenue for future research in order to find strong perfect metro domination.

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